

The influence of propeller skew on cavitation noise: a numerical study

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Abstract. The omnipresent demand for propulsion efficiency is accompanied by growing concerns about increasing underwater noise emissions by shipping. Noise reduction strategies mostly aim to reduce the cavitation occurrence altogether, but can entail significant efficiency losses. The present study investigates options to manipulate the cavitation noise at its cause. It builds on the acoustic monopole and focusses on alleviating the cavitation volume acceleration as the driver of sound pressure rather than the volume amplitude. Among the geometric parameters, skew does not in itself affect the open-water propulsion characteristics significantly. However, it influences the behaviour of cavitation on blades in inhomogeneous inflow. Its role in cavitation noise reduction is investigated by RANS simulations with a VoF approach. The E779A model propeller is modified with regard to its radial skew distribution and operated in two different wake fields. Based on the calculated vapour volume, the emitted sound pressure is deduced and analysed.

While the original propeller shows a well-developed partial sheet cavitation, which collapses rapidly transiting to tip vortex cavitation when leaving the wake peak, the additional skew leads to a moderate sheet cavitation occurrence, a smoother transfer into the tip vortex cavitation and thus to significantly lower noise emissions. The two wake fields provide insights into the sensitivity of cavitation behaviour towards changes of the inflow conditions and into the effect of simultaneous occurrence on adjacent blades. The study thus contributes to a more cause-related strategy of propeller noise mitigation with focus on the first seven harmonics of the blade passing frequency.

Key words: cavitation noise, inhomogeneous wake field, propeller noise, skew variation, acoustic monopole, multi-phase simulation

1. Introduction

The increasing underwater noise emissions in the oceans are primarily caused by the cavitating propellers of merchant ships and are attracting growing attention of shipping companies and authorities [1]. Sheet cavitation, the most common form associated with high sound levels, is considered to have a dominant influence on the low-frequency range of the spectrum, while the often accompanying tip vortex cavitation is associated with higher-frequency ranges [2]. The raised noise levels underwater affect marine mammals by masking their vocalisations and as an additional stressor among other marine pollutants [3, 4]. In view of the challenges of climate and species protection, modern propeller design is no longer allowed to choose between high energy efficiency or low noise emissions. These prerequisites can only be met with a thorough understanding of the noise generating mechanisms involved in the cavitation occurrence on propeller blades in inhomogeneous inflow.

The acoustic monopole was introduced in the context of cavitation noise by Huse [5] and Ross [6]. It has been widely accepted [7] as an appropriate model for unsteady sheet cavitation occurring due to a significantly increased angle of attack for the propeller blade passing through the wake field trough. Ji et al. [8] confirmed this numerically for a conventional propeller and Pereira et al. [9] experimentally for the model propeller used in this study. It enables a direct link between the cavitation behaviour and the corresponding sound pressure. Previous studies [10, 11] applied this model to deduce the cavitation volume

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evolution from measured pressure fluctuations and provided a typical temporal course for the cavitation volume during a blade passage through the wake trough. The collapse process of the sheet cavitation found as an explanation of the often described *hump* around 50 Hz in shipping noise spectra that tends to exceed perspective limit curves for underwater radiated noise (URN) [12].

In this study, the benchmark model propeller *E779A* [13] was chosen to employ the acoustic monopole model for the interpretation of numerical simulations with regard to cavitation noise generation in the lower frequency range between the blade passing frequency (BPF) and its seven higher harmonics. The model propeller is well suited for this purpose, firstly, as it has a comparatively small skew angle and shows well developed sheet cavitation at typical cavitation numbers. Furthermore, the broad basis of experimental and numerical studies on its cavitation behaviour allow a detailed validation of the applied numerical model. Starting from extensive experiments in homogeneous and inhomogeneous inflow [9, 13], several studies analysed the capabilities of different numerical methods [14, 15] of capturing the cavitation behaviour. In summary, the numerical studies confirm Reynolds-averaged Navier-Stokes (RANS) simulations to capture the fluctuating cavitation reasonably well, though inherently less detailed than Detached-Eddy (DES) or Large-Eddy (LES) simulations which require extensive numerical resources.

The skew as one global parameter of the propeller blade geometry was analysed at open-water conditions by Asnaghi et al. [16] and Bal [17] comprising only steady cavitation patterns without acoustic aspects. Ji et al. [18] compared two propellers with different skew angles in inhomogeneous inflow including the application of the monopole concept, also applied in their preceding study [19]. There, the high-skew propeller is found to be quieter than the conventional one. The present study adopts this approach with a parametric model in order to keep all other geometric parameters unchanged, apart from the skew. Furthermore, the general observation is viewed more detailed by applying two wake fields that differ in breadth and depth of their trough.

After outlining the applied numerical model, the corresponding mesh study and a validation case in Section 2, the results with regard to cavitation behaviour, noise emissions and propulsion characteristics are presented in Section 3 including insights into the tip vortex structures. These are discussed and summarized in the final sections.

2. Numerical model

The model propeller *E779A* with its dimensions given in Table 1 was set up as a parametric CAD model. Thus, it is possible to vary its geometry systematically as performed in the present study by applying an additional skew distribution increasing the overall skew angle from 10.4° to 35.5° . The skew distribution, only roughly described by the skew angle, was designed to produce both a curved leading and trailing edge in order to prolong the cavitation occurrence on the blade compared to the original propeller. Given limitations for highly loaded single propellers with regard to strength, the chosen angle was considered a realistic, but pronounced example. Both propellers are depicted in Figure 1 and are referred to as the *original* and the *skewed* propeller in the following report. Radial lines are marked in the following figures at $r/R = 0.7, 0.8, 0.9$ and 0.95 for ease of reference.

Figure 1. Original (left, dashed line) and skewed propeller geometry (centre, solid line) with their projected outlines (right) in mm

The propellers operate in a quasi-cylindrical computational domain with inlet / outlet boundary conditions at the respective parallel faces and a no-slip condition at the circular boundary surface. By means of a user-defined velocity distribution on the inlet surface, the inhomogeneous inflow resembling the wake field cause by a ship hull is generated (details given in Section 2.3) The propellers are enclosed in a cylindrical rotating mesh region as shown in Figure 2.

Both propellers are analysed at an operation point defined by the mean inflow velocity $u_0 = 5.808$ m/s, the rotation rate $n = 30.5$ s⁻¹ and the cavitation number $\sigma = 3.5$, defined by the ambient pressure p , the vapour pressure of water p_v and the dynamic pressure including the water density ρ as

$$\sigma = \frac{p - p_v}{\frac{1}{2} \rho u_0^2} \quad (1)$$

Table 1. Propeller dimensions [13]

Diameter D	227.27 mm	Rake (nominal)	4°35' (forward)
Number of blades	4	Expanded area ratio	0.689
Pitch ratio (nominal)	1.1	Hub diameter at $x = 0$	45.53 mm
Skew angle	10.4° (original)	Hub length	68.30 mm

Figure 2. Setup of computational domain: radius of outer cylinder is $4 D$, distance from inlet face to propeller plane is $1.1 D$, length of domain is $6.6 D$

2.1. Governing equations

The presented simulations are performed in the OpenFOAM framework (v2406) with the solver *interPhaseChangeDyMFoam* [20]. The numerical model employs the RANS equations for incompressible, multiphase flow given by the continuity and momentum equations:

$$\frac{\partial \rho_m}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_m \mathbf{U}) = 0 \quad (2)$$

$$\frac{\partial (\rho_m \mathbf{U})}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\rho_m \mathbf{U} \mathbf{U}) = -\nabla p + \nabla \cdot (\mu_{eff} (\nabla \mathbf{U} + \nabla \mathbf{U}^T)) \quad (3)$$

$$\rho_m = \rho_l \alpha_l + \rho_v (1 - \alpha_l) \quad (4)$$

The indices l and v distinguish the liquid and vapour phases respectively with m referring to their mixture, denoting the volume fraction α and the density ρ . The velocity vector is denoted by \mathbf{U} , the local pressure by p and the effective viscosity by μ_{eff} .

Based on the PIMPLE algorithm, the **k- ω SST** turbulence model was used with the corresponding wall function for $y^+ > 30$. The time discretization was based on the Euler approach, the second order upwind method was applied for convective and diffusive terms. The mass transfer \dot{m} in the volume-of-fluid (VoF) method is captured by the Schneer-Sauer cavitation model described by the equations for evaporation and condensation, controlled by coefficients C_v and C_c , respectively, with the generic bubble radius R_B and the volume fraction of bubble nuclei α_{Nuc} . Table 2 gives an overview over the applied coefficients.

$$\frac{\partial \alpha_v}{\partial t} + \nabla \cdot (\alpha_v \mathbf{U}) = \frac{\dot{m}}{\rho_v} \quad (5)$$

$$\dot{m} = \begin{cases} C_c \alpha_l (1 - \alpha_l) \frac{3 \rho_v \rho_l}{\rho_m R_B} \sqrt{\frac{2(p_v - p)}{3 \rho_l}}, & \text{if } p_v > p \\ C_v \alpha_l (1 + \alpha_{Nuc} - \alpha_l) \frac{3 \rho_v \rho_l}{\rho_m R_B} \sqrt{\frac{2(p - p_v)}{3 \rho_l}}, & \text{if } p_v \leq p \end{cases} \quad (6)$$

Table 2. Coefficients for the numerical model

ω	5.903 s ⁻¹	C_c	1.0	α_{Nuc}	1.0 · 10 ¹¹
k	0.06 m ² /s ²	C_v	1.0	R_B	5.0 · 10 ⁻⁶ mm

The total volume of the vapour phase was computed by a weighted volume integral comprising all cells in the rotating mesh zone. Additionally, a control volume enclosing one blade was employed in order to capture only the cavitation volume of that individual blade. The resulting volume signal was post-processed by application of the acoustic monopole model describing the correlation between a temporally varying volume V (or rather the curvature of its graph) and the generated sound pressure p with the water density ρ and the receiver distance s .

$$p(t) = \frac{\rho \ddot{V}(t)}{4 \pi s} \quad (7)$$

2.2. Grid generation

With the focus of this study on underwater noise emissions, these were necessarily chosen as the convergence criterium for the required mesh resolution. So, instead of an otherwise typical analysis of converging propulsion characteristics, each refinement step was analysed with regard to the sound pressure levels obtained according to Equation (7). The mesh refinement comprised four nested regions, the innermost, i.e. finest two shown in Figure 3.

A cylinder surrounding the shaft and the rotating mesh zone formed the first level of refinement of the basic mesh of the outer domain. The rotating mesh zone itself contains an even finer mesh, while the blade surface and a ring enclosing all blade tips were meshed with the second, but smallest cell size of 1.0 mm.

Figure 3. Mesh refinement around blade tips and tip vortex for the original propeller: cells of refinement regions (grey) filtered by their volume based on an edge length of 1 mm (left) and 0.5 mm (right).

During the refinement iterations, the importance of the transition from sheet cavitation to the consecutive tip vortex cavitation became apparent (details in Section 3.1). Consequently, the helix-shaped region of each tip vortex starting at the blade tip was refined iteratively in length and cell size to 0.5 mm in order to provide the tip vortex cavitation with sufficient finely meshed space to develop. The refinement process concluded when no further increase in the harmonics of the sound pressure spectrum was found. Note that the focus on relevant contributions to the sound spectrum in combination with the inherent constraints of RANS simulations with regard to vortex resolution limited the employed refinement further down the tip vortex helix.

2.3. Modelling the wake field

In view of the comparative focus of this study and the adaptation of the experimental setup reported by Pereira et al. [9], the inhomogeneous axial inflow was simulated by imposing an inhomogeneous velocity distribution to the inlet boundary condition as performed in similar numerical studies [18, 19, 21]. The axial velocity and the resulting nominal wake field are shown in Figure 4. Numerical and physical diffusion of the velocity gradient from the inlet towards the propeller plane was accounted for by exaggerating the gradient of the velocity distribution at the inlet face iteratively. The free-stream velocity is slightly higher for the broad wake field to achieve identical mean axial velocities in both wake fields (note additional iso-line in the left-hand plot of Figure 5).

Figure 4. Detail view of the inhomogeneous inflow from the inlet boundary, exemplarily for the original propeller in the broad wake field. The iso-lines represent the axial velocity component.

Figure 5. Broad (*left*) and narrow (*right*) wake fields evaluated for the propeller disk at $x = 0.2 D$ in front of the propeller plane, represented by iso-lines of the axial velocity. Radial coordinate normalized with the propeller radius.

Two different wake field were created in order to compare their respective influence on the acoustic behaviour of the two propellers. As outlined in Figure 5, they differ in the prominence and tangential width of the wake trough around the 12 o'clock position, referred to as *broad* and *narrow*. The broad wake field is adapted from an experimental wake field generated by a stack of plates in front of the propeller [9]. The narrow wake field is intended to resemble a typical wake field of a single-screw merchant ship.

2.4. Validation case

Experimental data as reported in the benchmark study [15] were used to validate the described numerical model. An operation point with homogeneous inflow was implemented with a rotation rate $n = 36 \text{ s}^{-1}$, an inflow velocity $u_0 = 5.808 \text{ m/s}$ and a cavitation number $\sigma_n = 1.763$, here defined based on the circumferential speed as $\sigma_n = (p - p_v)/(0.5 \rho n^2 D^2) = \sigma \cdot J^2$ with Equation (1) and (8). The propulsion characteristics are found in good agreement with the experimental data as listed in Table 3 with the advance coefficient J , the thrust coefficient k_T and the torque coefficient k_Q given by:

$$J = \frac{u_0}{n D} \quad (8)$$

$$k_T = \frac{T}{\rho n^2 D^4} \quad (9)$$

$$k_Q = \frac{Q}{\rho n^2 D^5} \quad (10)$$

Table 3. Results of the validation case at $J = 0.71$

	Experiment	Simulation	Relative deviation
k_T	0.2559	0.2575	0.63 %
$10 k_Q$	0.4636	0.4551	-1.83 %
η_0	0.6237	0.6394	2.51 %

The stationary cavitation pattern was compared to high-speed photos from the experiment based on the iso-surface of the vapour fraction $\alpha_v = 0.5$ as shown in Figure 6. Both sheet cavitation and adjacent tip vortex cavitation agree well with the experimental observation notwithstanding a more elongated tip vortex cavitation in the experiment. Note that the region of the hub vortex was not subject to mesh refinement with the focus of the study lying on the fluctuating cavitation types on the blades. Therefore, the comparatively coarse mesh behind the hub does not capture vapour fraction.

Figure 6. Comparison of numerical (*left*) and experimental cavitation pattern (*right*): iso-surfaces for $\alpha_v = 0.5$ (*blue*) and 0.9 (*light blue*) at $\sigma_n = 1.763$ and $J = 0.71$. Photo reprinted with permission.

3. Results

3.1. Cavitation behaviour

Figure 7 shows the evolution of the cavitation volume during one blade passage through the upper wake field region and links it to the corresponding cavitation pattern based on the iso-surface of the vapour fraction $\alpha_v = 0.5$ in Figure 8 and 9. As can be seen from the graph, the sum of the vapour fraction follows the typical course with a moderate increase and a rapid decrease as documented experimentally for the original propeller [9], but also for a typical blade passage of a full-scale container ship propeller [10].

Attention has to be paid to the final phase of the volume decrease, when the developed sheet cavitation is transferred into the adjacent tip vortex (see Figure 8 and 9). On reaching its full extent at $\Phi = 10^\circ$ or 20° respectively, the sheet cavitation elongates into the tip vortex forming a contiguous cavity, which then increases in length and size while the attached sheet cavitation and also the overall vapour volume diminish. However, instead of decreasing completely before building up with the next blade passage, the volume graph contains a plateau, which indicates that the remaining vapour fraction is conserved temporarily within the tip vortex before dissolving fully. It is this plateau that became more and more pronounced through the mesh refinement iterations described in Section 2.2. It distorts the smooth fade-out of the volume graph of the respective blade by inducing a much stronger curvature and, thus, enlarges the tonal components in the sound pressure spectrum, especially at the third to seventh harmonics of the blade passing frequency, outlined further in the next section.

The two propellers match in their general cavitation behaviour, although the skewed propeller's cavitation pattern comprises a significantly smaller volume amplitude over a larger angular range. At its maximum extent, the sheet cavitation does not cover radii $r < 0.75 R$, even if this part of the blade shows cavitation when entering the wake trough (right-hand blade in frame $\Phi = 58^\circ$ in Figure 9). The plateau corresponding to the transition into tip vortex cavitation occurs for the skewed propeller as well, though less pronounced. The volume increase involved in this plateau can be examined more closely by assigning the corresponding vapour volume to each blade (dotted lines in Figure 7). The vapour volume of the blade leaving the wake trough is temporarily prevented from decreasing further, including in contrast a slight growth. This increase, concurrent with a high curvature, becomes even more pronounced in the overall vapour volume due to the overlap with the inception cavitation on the next blade entering the wake through.

Figure 7. Cavitation volume evolution in total (*solid lines*) and for individual blades (*dotted lines*) of both propellers in the broad wake field and in total for the narrow wake field (*dashed lines*), exemplary instances depicted in Figure 8 (i) and 9 (i).

Note that the vapour fraction of the tip vortex cavitation detaches from the blade tip and remains in the region of the inflow velocity gradient.

The influence of the wake field characteristic can be observed by comparing the solid and the dashed lines of Figure 7. While both propellers maintain their respective behaviour as described above, the effect of a broad region of reduced inflow velocity, corresponding to a higher angle of attack for the propeller blade, compared to a more narrow region is evident. Both propellers develop a significantly larger cavitation extent in the broad wake field than in the narrow one. However, even in the narrow wake field, the above described plateau is faintly discernible at the end of the volume decrease, while the temporal overlap of cavitation on adjacent blades is inherently reduced in the narrow wake field.

Figure 8. Cavitation pattern of the original propeller in the broad wake field: iso-surface of the vapour fraction $\alpha_v = 0.5$. The iso-lines represent the nominal wake field as shown in Figure 4.

Figure 9. Cavitation pattern of the skewed propeller in the broad wake field: iso-surface of the vapour fraction $\alpha_v = 0.5$. The iso-lines represent the nominal wake field as shown in Figure 4.

3.2. Deduced noise emissions

Following Equation (7), the volume signals presented in the previous sections were differentiated twice with respect to time in order to deduce the corresponding sound pressure. By applying a Fast-Fourier-Transform, the spectra of the sound pressure levels (SPL) were derived as depicted in Figure 10. The cavitation volume signal comprising the vapour fraction of all solved time steps inevitably contains numerical noise, which intensifies during the double-differentiation. Accompanying tests have confirmed the spectrum to be unaffected by this noise up to the seventh harmonic of the blade passing frequency. Thus, the interpretation of the sound pressure level spectra is limited to the range of the first seven harmonics.

Figure 10. SPL spectra for both propellers and both wake fields: Frequency axis normalized with the blade passing frequency (122 Hz), frequency resolution $\Delta f = 30.5 \text{ Hz} = \frac{1}{4} \text{ BPF}$

As can be seen from the graph, in the broad wake field the skewed propeller causes sound pressure levels approximately 5 to 10 dB lower than the original propeller over the relevant frequency range. The narrow wake field enables generally lower levels at all tonal peaks of the spectrum. The difference between the two propellers is less pronounced here and mainly perceptible at 2 and 3 BPF. In view of the time signals of Figure 7, the difference between the two propellers in the narrow wake field lies mainly in the amplitude and length of the main hump, but not in the curvature of the collapse phase. This corresponds to the findings of the mesh study attributing the plateau of the volume graph to 3 to 7 BPF.

Another aspect influencing the curvature and correspondingly the sound pressure is the overlap of the cavitation occurrence on consecutive blades. Figure 7 shows the contribution of the growing bubble to the curvature in course of the collapsing predecessor. Thus, in the narrow wake field the individual volume evolutions overlap less and therefore less curvature develops at the transition to tip vortex cavitation, resulting in lower levels at 3 to 7 BPF.

3.3. Propulsion characteristics

Both propeller variants were analysed in open-water cases, which comprised four operation points each. The advance coefficient J was stepped from 0.6 to 0.8 by altering the rotation rate. The results are compared to experimental data [13] as displayed in Figure 11. In conformity with the benchmark study [15], a certain difference between numerical and experimental results can be noted for the original propeller as also stated for the validation case in Section 2.4, partly expectable due to different Reynold numbers.

The two geometries are identical in parameters influencing the propulsion characteristics decisively (radial sections, pitch distribution). The skew only shifts the blade sections tangentially and axially without altering their angle of attack and their respective contribution to thrust and torque. This theoretical consideration is reflected in the numerical results of Figure 11, where a close agreement between the two propellers can be noted within the range of accuracy of the numerical model discussed above.

Figure 11. Open-water characteristics of the original (*black*) and skewed propeller (*red*) with $Re = 1.5 \cdot 10^8$ compared to experimental data (*blue*) with $Re = 7 \cdot 10^7$ (a) and $2 \cdot 10^8$ (b) [13]: thrust coefficient (*solid* / *), torque coefficient (*dashed* / o) and efficiency (*dotted* / x)

3.4. Tip vortex structure

From the previous sections it becomes apparent that the conservation of a residual vapour volume during the transition from sheet in to tip vortex cavitation plays a central role with regard to underwater noise emissions as it forms a plateau in the volume graph and thus increases the latter's curvature. The study [10] concerning a volume evolution derived from pressure fluctuations of a full-scale container vessel where a similar plateau was found, several explanatory approaches were named, e.g. the rebounding of the collapsing cavitation bubble as documented in [22]. However, the numerical model underlying this study does not consider undissolved gas as the basis for a bubble rebound. The mechanisms captured by the equations outlined in Section 2.1 involve only low pressure as the reason for vapour to be generated or maintained.

Figure 12. Top view of vortex structure at the end of the volume collapse with iso-surfaces for the vapour fraction $\alpha_v = 0.5$ (*blue*) and the Q-criterion $Q = 5 \cdot 10^4$ (*grey*) – original propeller, broad wake field

This shifts the focus of further investigation towards the tip vortex being the location of the remaining vapour volume in question. As the pressure within a vortex is closely linked to its circulation, the Q-criterion was employed to illustrate the vortex structure around the tip vortex cavitation. Figure 12 shows the development of the vapour fraction and the Q-criterion iso-surfaces at the end of the volume decrease. A pronounced tip vortex exists that emerges from the upper end of the leading edge and contains the tip vortex cavitation. As the blade moves through the gradient of the wake field towards the region of unimpeded inflow, a secondary vortex emerges from the pressure side of the trailing edge and spirals around the main vortex while the remaining tip vortex cavitation is conserved within the latter. Note in reference to Figure 8 ($\Phi = 40^\circ$) that during this process the transition into tip vortex cavitation is completed. When the blade exits the wake trough, both the secondary vortex and the remaining tip vortex cavitation disappear. Throughout the lower part of the circular blade path and up again into the trough, the typical single-vortex shape persists. Similar vortex structures were observed for the skew propeller and also in the narrow wake field, though smaller, indicating these structures to be a physical effect rather than a numerical artefact.

4. Discussion

The presented cavitation behaviour of both propellers agrees substantially with the evolution of sheet cavitation extent reported in several experimental and numerical studies [8, 9, 11, 18]. The rapid volume decrease or, more precisely, the high volume acceleration at the end of the sheet cavitation collapse causes the largest sound pressure peaks. The adjacent plateau at the end of the collapse phase has not been reported in [18] notwithstanding the similar methodical approach, but an underestimation of the tip vortex cavitation is mentioned in the study. A comparison in the frequency domain is not possible, also because the preceding study only focusses on the first three harmonics [19]. Capturing this part of the cavitation process during a blade passage through the wake trough is essential for sufficient representation of the higher harmonics in the deduced sound pressure spectrum as shown by the mesh study. Both the larger skew angle and the narrow wake field lead to a reduction of sound pressure levels in the considered frequency range.

This study renews the observation made during the analysis of full-scale pressure fluctuations with regard to the plateau adjacent to the main volume decrease reported in [10]. The subsequent study [11] links the collapse process to the higher harmonics of the blade passing frequency agreeing with the observations in model scale presented above. Taking into account the stochastic nature of propeller cavitation, not realistically represented by the inherently stable conditions in the numerical domain, the transition or collapse process of the sheet cavitation described above is also linked to the omnipresent broadband *hump* of shipping noise at approximately 50 Hz [12].

Another aspect of the cavitation behaviour in unsteady inflow conditions is the inertia of the bubble growth via evaporation. The comparison of a homogenous inflow case with an advance coefficient comparable to the trough of the broad wake field shows that under transient conditions, the cavitation does not reach the extent shown in the homogeneous case. It appears to have not enough time to grow before the blade leaves the region of lower inflow velocities, whereas the vortex structure temporally adapts the shape corresponding to the reduced inflow. This inertia may contribute to the smaller extent of cavitation in the narrow wake field in addition to the milder wake trough, i.e. a smaller change of the angle of attack.

By depicting the cavitation pattern, the transition of the sheet cavitation into the tip vortex cavitation can be identified as the underlying process. It involves a dual-strand shape of the tip vortex comprising a pronounced leading edge vortex with an additional trailing edge vortex. Reports of similar vortex structures emerging from the blade tip are scarcely found in literature. Berger et al. [23] report separate leading edge and local tip vortices merging into one vortex at the trailing edge. Additionally, similarity is found on hovering helicopter rotor blades as reported by Goertler et al. [24]. During intermediate changes in pitch though without cavitation and its inherent displacement of water on the suction side, similar inhomogeneous flow conditions lead a principal agreement with regard to the tip vortex structures. The helicopter rotor shows several vortices emerging from its blade tip at large pitch angle which correspond to the wake trough passage of the propellers, merging into one pronounced tip vortex further downstream. Though not necessarily constituting a causal link in itself, the coincidence of a more complex tip vortex structure associated with the maximum angle of attack and a high volume acceleration due to a plateau of the volume graph is remarkable, the interaction of the vortices needs to be examined further.

5. Conclusions

By applying numerical methods of limited computational effort, the present study outlines two important parameters influencing the cavitation noise of propellers in inhomogeneous inflow. Additional skew moderates the cavitation behaviour and the corresponding noise emissions, especially when broad wake troughs provide sufficient exposure time for the sheet cavitation to develop comprehensively. While limited in its extent by strength issues like bending or torsion, the skew offers noise reduction potential without endangering the efficiency necessarily. Besides, the wake field trough is confirmed to play an important role for the propeller's cavitation behaviour. Accordingly, the noise reduction potential of exiting wake-equalizing devices may further be investigated.

The acoustic monopole applied as shown to the volume evolution underlines the significance of the volume acceleration when investigating cavitation noise generation. The presented findings allow detailed insight into the process of noise generation in course of the transition from sheet cavitation to tip vortex cavitation. This process was found directly linked to 3 to 7 BPF. Accordingly, the prediction of these harmonics and the corresponding *hump* in the SPL spectra depend significantly on the detailed resolution of the collapse process in order to represent the volume graph's curvature sufficiently. Avoiding or reducing the sheet cavitation extent, which can hardly be achieved without efficiency loss, may not be necessary if the collapse or rather transition behaviour can be controlled closely. The development of multi-strand tip vortices will be subject to further research regarding the conservation of vapour volume within the tip vortex and the spacial and temporal development of the circulation around the blade and of the tip vortex.

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References

- [1] Rienk Terweij. *Ship Efficiency and Underwater Radiated Noise*. Transport Canada, Ottawa, 2023.
- [2] Kai Abrahamsen. The ship as an underwater noise source. In *Proceedings of the 11th European Conference on Underwater Acoustics*, Proceedings of Meetings on Acoustics, page 070058. Acoustical Society of America, 2012. doi: 10.1121/1.4772953.
- [3] Megan F. McKenna, Donald Ross, Sean M. Wiggins, and John A. Hildebrand. Underwater radiated noise from modern commercial ships. *Journal of the Acoustic Society of America*, 131(1):92–103, 2012. doi: 10.1121/1.3664100.
- [4] Scott Veirs, Val Veirs, Jason D. Wood, and Magnus Johnson. Ship noise extends to frequencies used for echolocation by endangered killer whales. *PeerJ*, 4:e1657, 2016. doi: 10.7717/peerj.1657.
- [5] Erling Huse. *Pressure fluctuations on the hull induced by cavitating propellers*. Number 111 in Norwegian Ship Model Experiment Tank publication. Trondheim, 1972.
- [6] Donald Ross. *Mechanics of underwater noise*. Peninsula Publishing, Westport, 1987.
- [7] The Specialist Committee on Cavitation Induced Pressure Fluctuation. Final Report and Recommendations to the 22nd ITTC. In *22nd International Towing Tank Conference*, 1999.
- [8] Bin Ji, Xianwu Luo, Xiaoxing Peng, Yulin Wu, and Hongyuan Xu. Numerical analysis of cavitation evolution and excited pressure fluctuation around a propeller in non-uniform wake. *International Journal of Multiphase Flow*, 43:13–21, 2012. doi: 10.1016/j.ijmultiphaseflow.2012.02.006.
- [9] Francisco Alves Pereira, Fabio Di Felice, and Francesco Salvatore. Propeller Cavitation in Non-Uniform Flow and Correlation with the Near Pressure Field. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 4(4):70, 2016. doi: 10.3390/jmse4040070.

- [10] Leonie S. Föhring, Peter Møller Juhl, and Dietrich Kurt Wittekind. Cavitation volume behaviour derived from full-scale pressure fluctuations. *Ships and Offshore Structures*, 18(4):541–549, 2022. doi: 10.1080/17445302.2022.2053353.
- [11] Leonie S. Föhring, Peter Møller Juhl, and Dietrich Kurt Wittekind. On the Influence of Cavitation Volume Variations on Propeller Broadband Noise. *Journal of Marine Science and Engineering*, 10(12):1946, 2022. doi: 10.3390/jmse10121946.
- [12] Max Schuster, Johanna M. Daniel, Dietrich Kurt Wittekind, and Leonie S. Föhring. Future requirements for ships to limit underwater noise in the oceans. In *116th Congress of the German Society for Maritime Technology*, volume 1, Hamburg, 2022. Schiffbautechnische Gesellschaft e.V.
- [13] Francesco Salvatore, Francisco Alves Pereira, Mario Felli, Danilo Calcagni, and Fabio Di Felice. *Description of the INSEAN E779A Propeller Experimental Dataset*. Number 2006-085. INSEAN Propulsion and Cavitation laboratory, Rome, Italy, 2006.
- [14] Zhi-feng Zhu. Characteristic correlation between propellers cavitating wake and cavitation noise. *Applied Acoustics*, 81:31–39, 2014. doi: 10.1016/j.apacoust.2014.02.004.
- [15] Guilherme Vaz, David Hally, Tobias Huuva, Norbert Bulten, Pol Muller, Paolo Becchi, Jose L. R. Her-
rer, Steward Whitworth, Romain Macé, and Andrei Korsström. Cavitating Flow Calculations for the
E779A Propeller in Open Water and Behind Conditions: Code Comparison and Solution Validation.
In *Fourth International Symposium on Marine Propulsors*, 2015.
- [16] Abolfazl Asnaghi, Urban Svennberg, and Rickard E. Bensow. Numerical and experimental analysis
of cavitation inception behaviour for high-skewed low-noise propellers. *Applied Ocean Research*, 79:
197–214, 2018. doi: 10.1016/j.apor.2018.07.010.
- [17] Şakir Bal. Numerical Investigation of Propeller Skew Effect on Cavitation. *Journal of ETA Maritime
Science*, 7(2):127–136, 2019. doi: 10.5505/jems.2019.08860.
- [18] Bin Ji, Xianwu Luo, and Yulin Wu. Unsteady cavitation characteristics and alleviation of pressure
fluctuations around marine propellers with different skew angles. *Journal of Mechanical Science and
Technology*, 28(4):1339–1348, 2014. doi: 10.1007/s12206-013-1166-8.
- [19] Bin Ji, Xianwu Luo, Xin Wang, Xiaoxing Peng, Yulin Wu, and Hongyuan Xu. Unsteady Numerical
Simulation of Cavitating Turbulent Flow Around a Highly Skewed Model Marine Propeller. *Journal
of Fluids Engineering*, 133(1), 2011. doi: 10.1115/1.4003355.
- [20] SIMFLOW Technologies. interPhaseChangeDyMFoam - OpenFOAM Solver, 2025. URL <https://help.sim-flow.com/solvers/inter-phase-change-dym-foam>.
- [21] Chengzao Han, Yun Long, Xiaorui Bai, and Bin Ji. Numerical Investigation of Unsteady Cavitation
Flow around E779A Propeller in a Nonuniform Wake with an Insight on How Cavitation Influences
Vortex. *Shock and Vibration*, 2021(1), 2021. doi: 10.1155/2021/5577517.
- [22] Y.-C. Wang and Christopher Earls Brennen. The Noise Generated by the Collapse of a Cloud of
Cavitation Bubbles. In Steven L. Ceccio, Akinori Furukawa, and J. H. Kim, editors, *Cavitation and
gas-liquid flow in fluid machinery and devices*, 1995, volume 226 of *FED*, pages 17–29. American
Society of Mechanical Engineers, New York, NY, 1995.
- [23] Stephan Berger, Rasmus Møller Bering, Max Steden, Keun Woo Shin, and Jens Ring Nielsen, editors.
*Numerical study on the evolution of vortex structures at the propeller tip and their influence on cavi-
tation inception: Norwegian University of Science and Technology, Department of Marine Technology*,
2024. doi: 10.15480/882.9347.
- [24] Andreas Goertler, Johannes N. Braukmann, C. Christian Wolf, Anthony D. Gardner, and Markus Raf-
fel. Blade Tip-Vortices of a Four-Bladed Rotor with Axial Inflow. *Journal of the American Helicopter
Society*, 65(4):1–13, 2020. doi: 10.4050/JAHS.65.042002.